

Burn Management in Resource-Limit Setting: Integration of Emergency Medicine, General Surgery, and Orthopedics

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Abstract: Objective: To investigate the effects of multidisciplinary team-based early rehabilitation model in patients with burns in resource-limit settings.

Methods: Totally 104 cases of patients with extensive burns were enrolled and grouped into control group and intervention group using convenience sampling method, From January 2019 to December 2020 in Janakpur city. General aspects of inpatient treatment in Surgery department (burn ward) of MIHS provincial hospital Janakpur, Nepal accumulated burn patients were the research subjects. The data was analyzed using SPSS 16.0 statistical software for processing, statistical description using frequency, composition ratio, $\bar{x} \pm s$, statistical inference using t-test, repeated testing analysis of variance, chi square test, with $P < 0.05$ as statistical differences. Results: There were significant differences between two groups in hospital stay, medical expenses, ADL (Activities of Daily Living) and the quality of life between two groups ($P < 0.05$).

Conclusion: Multidisciplinary team-based early rehabilitation model can improve the quality of life and rehabilitation for patients with extensive burns in resource-limit settings.

Keywords: burn; early stage; multidiscipline; rehabilitation model

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Introduction

Burn management in developing countries encounters huge problems at any stage. Inadequate access to burn care facilities and a poorly-equipped health care system hinder optimal treatment. With no formal infection control policy in most low and middle-income country (LMIC) burn units and limited aseptic techniques for wound care management, due to nursing constraints and inadequate limited facilities, high rates of burn-related mortality and morbidity are still seen in developing countries [1]. This is further complicated by the patients' parents having to apply some of the dressings unsupervised, in less than ideal circumstances and by superstition, religious rituals and faith in alternative

medicine. Service provision for burns in most LMICs is mainly through the western system of care, considered to be the ultimate in patient care. The approach to burn management, however, has to be radically different from that in western countries. Certain well-tested, cost-effective treatment procedures need to be adopted to conserve resources and make the best of what is realistically available[2]. Overall poor conditions and lack of resources make excisional surgery impossible for a large percentage of patients. Unfortunately, only a handful of studies evaluating burn interventions in LMICs have been reported, possibly due to lack of the funding necessary to conduct such studies and partly due to lack of expertise in many of these LMICs[3].

The severity of the burn wound and its clinical manifestation depends not only on the treatment regime at the burn centre but also on first aid and initial management at the burn site, at the emergency department, and during transfer to the burn centre. Few population-based studies have been conducted in LMICs about the first aid to be provided and the subsequent healthcare-seeking for burns, along with methods of burn treatment at home[4]. Obviously, traditional values may determine the treatment of burn injuries in the home setting. Adequate immediate first aid following a burn appreciably determines outcome and limits tissue damage and subsequent morbidity, including the need for surgery. Cool running water at a temperature of between 10 and 15 °C for 20-30 min is considered adequate burn first-aid treatment[5]. In one study about burn treatment in LMICs, including all countries in sub-Saharan Africa, Latin America, and the Caribbean, the Middle East, India, and Nepal, as well as other countries in Asia and adjoining islands, cool water was applied to the burned area as a first-aid therapy in a third of the cases, ratio comparable to that observed in some high-income countries (HICs)[6]. Naturally, the availability of running water at the appropriate temperature, not universally readily available, in addition to proper education and knowledge, is an obvious limiting factor. Subsequently, since burn wounds are sterile immediately after injury but liable to rapid bacterial colonization, the wounds should be covered with a clean sterile sheet until dressed[7].

One-half to two-thirds of burned persons in LMICs are reported to be taken to a health care facility for treatment and a significant relationship is found between the size of the burn sustained and subsequent healthcare seeking. Those who seek healthcare have significantly deeper burns covering a wider TBSA or an infected burn previously treated at home. In the remaining cases that receive home treatment, non-tested household remedies are commonly used as a first-aid measure in developing countries. A traditional preparation is usually applied in the form of concoctions made of urine and mud, cow dung, beaten eggs, or mud and leaves[8]. A significant relationship is also found between the size of burn sustained and the type of home-based treatment. Superficial burns and those covering a small body surface area are treated with gentian violet, while more extensive burns are paradoxically treated with a traditional preparation. In a report from Turkey, after cold water and ice, raw egg white was most commonly used as first-aid treatment in addition to yogurt, toothpaste, tomato paste, or sliced potato. Most of these substances are harmful, seriously compounding the injury. Unfortunately, most people in Turkey as well as in other LMICs still believe that this kind of medicine is safer and less expensive than western medications and ointments. Early presentation and active resuscitation are the key to successful management of severe burns[9]. Among the components of initial management, fluid resuscitation has a crucial role in preventing complications and reducing the death rate. Initial care is in the line of the ABC of resuscitation. An adequate airway and respiration must be ensured. All patients except those with minor burns must receive fluid resuscitation based on a simple formula using the Parkland or Carvajal formulas for resuscitation[11]. In some situations, intravenous fluid replacement must be established prior to transfer to a burn centre - however, time should not be wasted to set up an intravenous infusion in the case of a short journey that is expected to take no more than 1 h. Unfortunately, such conditions may not be possible to achieve in developing countries[12]. First, a first-aid health care provider may not be available at the scene of a burn accident; second, adequate resuscitation at the scene may not be possible due to the considerable ignorance of health care providers about the correct and safe initial management of burns; and third, early transfer of patients may not be possible because of the lack of an available ambulance or other means of transport. A long journey during the shock period is in any case challenging and risky,

and delay for immediate urgent resuscitation or the treatment of life-threatening problems is the rule in most remote and rural areas and LMICs[13].

In fire disasters involving a large number of victims, good triage is the cornerstone of effective burn disaster management and should be performed at the disaster site by staff with knowledge of burn treatment, largely lacking in most LMICs. Adequate triage must take into consideration the total number of patients, bed availability, and transportation capacity[14]. Increased mortality rates associated with fire disasters in LMICs are due - in addition to limited resources and adequate facilities - to the lack of a proper burn disaster and rescue organization plan[15].

Local burn wound management is one of the most important aspects of burn therapy after the shock phase. Several methods of burn wound management are available today. Conventional dressings necessitate, however, topical antimicrobial ointments and creams that may be expensive or not available, and require frequent dressing changes. Economics and logistics dictate that alternatives to the relatively expensive burns dressings available in the developed world are required. In a developing country with a fairly large incidence of burns and with financial constraints and limited budgets where all medical resources are stretched beyond practical limits, a major factor that must be considered is how to reduce the cost of therapy and reach a cost-effective management. In LMICs an extremely simple, convenient, economical but effective dressing with a long shelf life is required. In addition treatment should be on an outpatient basis as much as possible so that the load on hospital beds is reduced. Pursuing conservative burn wound management and using amnion as a biological dressing seem to be an appropriate burn management in developing countries[16].

Increasingly aggressive surgical approaches with early tangential excision and wound closure are nowadays standard practice in burn units and probably represent the most significant change in recent years, leading to improvement in mortality rates of burn victims at a substantially lower cost. Early excision of burned skin was first advocated for small to moderate burns. Subsequently, tangential excision in repeated but frequent interventions and immediate skin cover with skin auto- or homografts were recommended for large burns[17]. By shortening hospital stay, early burn wound closure reduces infective complications. Faster healing decreases the severity of hypertrophic scarring, joint contractures, and stiffness and promotes quicker rehabilitation. However, lack of education in general and of health education in particular amongst the common people in the developing countries can hinder acceptance of this procedure and a lack of well-trained and motivated burns surgeons can worsen the situation as well. If proper facilities are lacking, if blood and other resources such as dressings are not available, and if health care providers are inadequately trained and prepared, such aggressive therapy in burn victims can induce further trauma and result in a less than optimal outcome. Moreover, without adequate skin cover by autografts, homografts, or other substitutes, the early excision of burned tissue is of no value. "Delayed primary" is the second best alternative to "early" burn wound excision and closure, with similar advantages of reducing the risk of septicaemia, mortality, morbidity, hospital stay, and cost of treatment. It should be preferred to "secondary" skin-grafting of granulating wounds. Thus, in the developing countries, indications of delayed primary burn surgery could be: unstable patients or those unfit for surgery during the first post-burn week; delay in transfer, delay in getting patient's consent for surgery; major burns with no available skin substitutes and lack of operating time[18]. Contraindications for delayed primary surgery are any sign of invasive sepsis or organ failure. Autografts from uninjured skin remain the mainstay of treatment. Severe burn patients, however, invariably lack adequate skin donor sites and not infrequently a temporary coverage needs to be applied following early tangential excision. While in HICs it is possible to collect homografts from cadavers, and skin banks have been created, in most LMICs this is not possible not only because of lack of expertise and facilities but most commonly because of social, cultural, and religious objections and certainly because of cost. In India, for example, harvesting cadaver skin is even forbidden by law[19]. Pig skin has been recommended instead, but in Muslim countries or in countries with a large Muslim population the use of porcine products is a sensitive issue, if not completely forbidden as well. Synthetic skin

replacement products are far too expensive to be of any value for management of severe burns in LMICs. BPPB have been developed as a substitute and though they are useful they are not comparable to allografts. Amnion or collagen sheets may be used instead. Another alternative would be harvesting skin from live donors - relatives in general. Though the idea seems appealing in some situations, one must not forget that the living donor will be another patient with partial-skin loss requiring treatment, further taxing already stretched and limited resources. It must be stressed that xenografts, allografts, and other synthetic or tissue-engineered replacements are only a temporary means of burn wound cover. True closure of deep and full-thickness burn wounds is achieved only with living autografts provided for coverage of extensive burn injuries by keratinocyte cultures (cultured epithelial autograft (CEA)), largely unavailable in most LMICs for obvious reasons. CEA is expensive to use and very sensitive to infection. It requires meticulous wound care and more professional time and effort than procedures with conventional autografts. Needless to say, even if the use of confluent sheets of CEA for the treatment of extensive third-degree burn wounds is considered to be definitely a life-saving procedure, long-term results have been disappointing and at present the true value of CEA is being questioned in most HIC burn centres. Better long-term coverage requires dermal replacement as well as epidermal replacement, which entails even more complex and expensive technologies. Early excisional surgery in most LMICs is thus impossible for a large percentage of extensive burn patients [20].

Research Methodology

Using the convenience sampling method, From January 2019 to December 2020 in Janakpur city General aspects of inpatient treatment in Surgery department (burn ward) of MIHS provincial hospital Janakpur, Nepal accumulated burn patients were the research subjects. The data was analyzed using SPSS 16.0 statistical software for processing, statistical description using frequency, composition ratio, statistical inference using t-test, $\bar{x} \pm s$, repeated testing analysis of variance, chi square test, with $P < 0.05$ as statistical differences.

Inclusion criteria: ① Age ≥ 18 years old, with burn types are Flame, Hydrothermal, Vapor, Hot Metal Thermal burns caused etc., burn area 50%~80% or deep II°, III° burn area exceeding 10%; ② Have clear consciousness, language expression; ③ Patients and their families know and agree to receive rehabilitation treatment; ④ no other basic diseases before injury.

Exclusion criteria: ① Failure to arrive within 48 hours after injury those who received early treatment; ② Early treatment failed, those with persistent wounds; ③ unable to actively cooperate with treatment healer.

Intervention method

This study adopted a non-contemporaneous control method, selecting 48 patients from January to December 2019 as the control group, 56 patients from January to December 2020 are the experimental group.

The control group was treated with conventional rehabilitation therapy, mainly consisting of rehabilitation therapists, through rehabilitation assessments a treatment mode mainly focused on functional exercise and other forms. Using routine treatment+routine care+routine rehabilitation, in future referred to as conventional mode. Among them, conventional treatment package including wound management, prevention and treatment of shock, prevention and treatment of infection, and Surgery, etc; Routine care mainly includes fluid replacement care wound care, infection care, preoperative and postoperative care Pain care, psychological care (establishing good patient care) relationship, listening, mentoring, and rehabilitation nursing (Rehabilitation, Suggestions and guidance), etc; Regular rehabilitation refers to medical care personnel provide health education and guidance to patients perform functional exercises on the affected limb, and the doctor requires the patient to enter perform rehabilitation exercises [6].

On the basis of conventional treatment mode in the experimental group establish a multidisciplinary approach led by responsible nurses team collaboration rehabilitation treatment work mechanism, forming a package including responsible physicians, responsible nurses, rehabilitation therapists psychological counselors, nutritionists, and social

workers rehabilitation treatment team, focusing on patients' physiology, psychology conduct comprehensive evaluation on social and other aspects, and carry out joint efforts ward rounds, rehabilitation assessments, development and implementation of centralized diagnosis and treatment a treatment measure that integrates nursing and rehabilitation. Meanwhile establishing a three-stage rehabilitation treatment for patients with extensive burns Ladder rehabilitation goals. ① First step, early goals: Maintain and gradually increase joint mobility at the injured area (Range of Motion, ROM), reducing scars Breast hyperplasia; ② Second tier, long-term goal: increase maximize avoidance by adding movement, flexibility, functionality, etc thrombosis; ③ The third ladder, ultimate goal: can complete daily activities such as standing and walking, achieve basic self-care in daily life. Based on each stage the goal is to dynamically adjust the rehabilitation plan in real time. Experiment all treatment methods in the group have been approved by the hospital ethics committee

It will be reviewed and approved. All team members have passed the 3-week burn rehabilitation knowledge training, within the training period inclusive rehabilitation assessment, physio therapy, occupational therapy Systematic content such as therapy, psychotherapy, and social support, Specific multidisciplinary team rehabilitation treatment model workflow the process and content are detailed.The measurement tools studied include: Data questionnaire, Barthel index scale, There are 3 parts of the Burn Health Scale (BSHS-B-Np) for nepali burns.

Data Collection Method

All team members underwent 3-week burn rehabilitation knowledge training and effectively collected research data. Patient baseline data were collected at the time of admission to the hospital,activities of daily living and quality of life don't Pass the Barthel Index Scale, Brief Burn Health Scale (BSHS-B-Np) at T1 (at admission),T2 (when the wound is basically healed, it means that the wound is basically the patients were asked at three time points), T3 (discharge).

Results and discussion

104 patients were selected, including 48 males, 56 female patients, aged 18-75, in the control group the burn area of the patient is (64.52 ± 10.46)%.The test group was (65.78 ± 14.03)%, with no statistical significance difference (t=0.362, P=0.779), others average information, age, gender, marital status, education level, payment method for medical expenses, and depth of burns. There was no statistically significant difference in degree comparison (P>0.05).

Table 1 Comparison of General Information between Two Groups of Patients ,Cases (%)

	Control group (n=48)	Experimental group (n=56)	X ² value	P value
Age(year)			1.347	0.508
18-30	8 (16.6)	11 (19.6)		
31-50	29 (60.5)	33 (58.9)		
51-75	11 (22.9)	12 (21.5)		
Gender			2.412	0.247
male	34 (66.6)	41 (73.3)		
female	14 (33.4)	15 (26.7)		
Marital status			0.093	0.776
married	41 (85.4)	46 (82.2)		
unmarried	7 (15.6)	10 (17.8)		
Education level			3.688	0.116
Primary school	11 (22.9)	14 (25.0)		

middle school	20 (41.6)	24 (42.8)		
high school	11 (22.9)	13 (23.2)		
junior college or above	6 (12.6)	5 (9.0)		
Payment method for medical expenses			2.245	0.393
medical insurance	40 (83.3)	46 (82.2)		
self funded	8 (16.7)	10 (17.8)		
Degree of burn			1.916	0.421
Deep I°	13 (27.1)	14 (25.0)		
Deep II°-III°	17 (35.4)	22 (39.2)		
III°	18 (37.5)	20 (35.7)		

Burn ward hospitalization time and total burn ward hospitalization cost there was a statistical difference between the two groups ($P < 0.05$); Burn ward there was no statistically significant difference in the cost of rehabilitation treatment between the two groups ($P > 0.05$), as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Burn ward hospitalization time and expenses of two groups of patients ($x \pm s$)

content	Experimental group (n=56)	Control group (n=48)	t-values	P value
hospitalization time (days)	34.21 ± 54.06	46.65 ± 34.35	2.713	0.004
Total cost of Burn ward hospitalization(USD)	558.38 ± 436.15	618.38 ± 440.15	2.224	0.035
Rehabilitation treatment cost(USD)	179.26 ± 163.16	182.26 ± 159.16	0.368	0.459

using the Barthel Index Scale at the time point, two groups of patients' daily living activities were evaluated based on compare the effects of two treatment modes on patients' daily life activities and the impact of mobility. Using two factor repeated measurements analysis of variance comparison of daily living activities between two groups of patients ability differences. Two factors, namely grouping factor G and timeliness interfactor T. Factor G includes two levels (real Test group G1 and control group G2), factor T includes three levels (T1 at admission, basic wound healing time T2, discharge time T3). Grouping factor G the Barthel index score main effect test showed significant ($F=36.180, P < 0.001$), indicating that there were two the comparison of differences between groups has statistical significance. The main effect of the inter factor T on this score is also consistent accounting significance ($F=151.128, P < 0.001$), mention as time progresses, both intervention modes can improve patients' daily activity water to varying degrees. Additionally, compare the grouping factor G with the time factor the interaction between elements T has statistically significant results ($F=31.219, P < 0.001$), indicating that the two are opposite to each other Simultaneous changes in Barthel index scores among group patients the effect is shown in Table 3.

Based on grouping factor G and time factor T significant interaction between levels, for two Perform a simple effect test, G at T1 and T2 Simple and effective Barthel index scores for two horizontal groups It should be checked that it is not significant, G is at the T3 level, and two Simple effect test of Barthel index score in group ($P < 0.001$), indicating the experimental group day at discharge the ability to engage in daily activities was significantly better than that of the control group the effectiveness of early multidisciplinary rehabilitation treatment models. At the G1 and G2 levels, Barthel refers to the simple effect test of numerical scores has statistical significance meaning ($P < 0.001$), indicating that

over time, there are two All modes are effective in improving patients' daily activity levels The effect of the experimental group is better than that of the control group to varying degrees group.

Table 3. Comparison of Barthel index scores at T1, T2, and T3 between the two groups of patients ($\bar{x} \pm s$, points)

	T1	T2	T3
Experimental group (n=56)	59.13+19.62	78.69 ± 17.38	92.31 ± 6.32
Control group (n=48)	54.90 ± 18.45	73.21 ± 15.14	86.11 ± 5.42
t-value	0.817	2.331	2.682
p-value	0.306	0.048	0.009

Quality of life of patients in both T1 and T2 stages the scores of all indicators in the evaluation are at a relatively low level, Perform statistical analysis between scores to obtain various indicators there was no statistically significant difference ($P > 0.05$) in the T3 stage during the quality of life assessment conducted, it was found that apart from psychological skills Statistics are available for all other items besides physical appearance the academic differences ($P < 0.05$) are detailed in Table 4.

Table 4 Comparison of Quality of Life between Two Groups of Patients at Discharge ($\bar{x} \pm s$, points)

	Control group (n=48)	Experimental group (n=56)	t-value	P value
physical functioning				
Independent activities	34.66 ± 13.40	44.89 ± 33.15	2.199	0.048
Function of the hand	10.94 ± 6.94	50.69 ± 34.71	3.686	0.001
Role Activity	6.13 ± 6.27	18.65 ± 23.62	2.289	0.046
psychological function				
Body image	20.72 ± 7.01	23.00 ± 6.14	1.916	0.338
emotion	62.18 ± 19.10	71.12 ± 20.15	2.447	0.038
social function				
family and friends	36.03 ± 10.32	64.52 ± 10.46	3.478	0.006
sex life	11.03 ± 3.82	51.51 ± 8.08	3.424	0.008
General health condition	32.29 ± 13.02	56.05 ± 21.03	3.335	0.019

surgery department of MIHS has implemented a multidisciplinary team since 2019 Collaborative rehabilitation therapy technology and adoption of standardized rehabilitation after rehabilitation treatment and evaluation techniques, patients with Patient's burn ward hospitalization time is longer than traditional rehabilitation Significant under the therapist led rehabilitation treatment model Shorten ($P < 0.05$). Physicians and patients are the most intuitive in terms of effectiveness The feeling is that most critically ill patients can walk out on their own . The main reason for the analysis is that our department has established a multidisciplinary collaborative team centered on patients, forming a rehabilitation treatment mechanism led by responsible nurses, Coordinate and optimize medical resources, carry out joint ward rounds, and promote health evaluate, develop and implement integrated diagnosis, treatment, nursing, and wellness integrating treatment measures to achieve rehabilitation care Comprehensive and systematic evaluation, treatment, and management, there is significant support and assistance for the effectiveness of rehabilitation treatment[21]. It can be seen that the transformation of rehabilitation concepts and models can provide the treatment outcomes of patients vary greatly. The cost of rehabilitation treatment is high in both the health center and patients Concerns[22]. From Table 2, it can be seen that the burn ward total cost of hospitalization has been implemented through multidisciplinary team rehabilitation there was a statistical difference before and after the treatment mode ($P < 0.05$). This is mainly related to the shortened hospitalization time in the burn ward. Many Intervention of early rehabilitation treatment models in disciplinary teams to some extent, it has reduced the economic burden on patients, It has good

economic benefits and will also save patients' lives In the future, some provinces will need to use deformity reduction and function The cost of rehabilitation is a profitable measure for doctors and patients.

The Barthel index of two groups of patients from admission to discharge grading span is large, and most of them are included in the study the patient is able to successfully complete control after the end of the rehabilitation period Urinary and bowel movements, bed and chair transfers, walking on level ground, and going upstairs ladder project. But at both T2 and T3 time points there is a difference ($P<0.05$), and the experimental group was discharged with the scores of the participants were higher than those of the control group, indicating that there were more early disciplinary rehabilitation nursing model for improving patients' daily lives. The ability to engage in daily activities has certain significance and helps to improve patients' ability to eat, bathe, dress, and dress ability in clothing and toileting.

Burn patients often fail due to various reasons it is difficult to get rid of the physical and mental effects of injury returning to society , therefore helping patients return to society it is the ultimate goal of burn rehabilitation [23,24]. For burn patients assessing the quality of life for individuals not only helps to understand the impact of burns on patients, while also affecting the clinical evaluate the effectiveness of bed treatment Collaborative provision of treatment plans and improvement in multidisciplinary fields establishing the necessary foundation for the quality of life of patients [25]. From Table 4 shows that intervention implementation began in the early stages after implementing the multi team rehabilitation, the two groups of patients there is a significant difference in quality of life at discharge, score analyzing, possible causes and targeting rehabilitation treatment plans full process psychological intervention and systematic social support related to holding factors. Therefore, early treatment and rehabilitation an integrated model is important for improving quality of life measures. This study also found that two groups of patients were discharged from the hospital comparison of physical images of mental health, no statistically significant difference ($P>0.05$). The cause may be a post burn condition the characteristics of the body image have undergone significant changes, and it is still necessary to improvement through long-term rehabilitation and plastic surgery, due to early intervention rehabilitation treatment mode long term adherence to multidisciplinary team rehabilitation therapy support is required to bring more significant results to patients.

Conclusion

This study aims to change the traditional single disciplinary rehabilitation treatment approach in resource-limit settings, adopting a holistic approach discipline guidance for rehabilitation therapists, and the role of medical members. The full process intervention of the medical team and psychological counseling. The support system for consultants teams has been established a multidisciplinary collaborative team centered on patients, with Strengthened collaboration between each other and expanded medical specialization in resource-limit settings.. By shortening the length of hospital stay reducing hospitalization costs and other factors have reduced patient experience economic burden, patient's ability to engage in daily living activities, and health ,the quality of life has also been improved, enabling rehabilitation treatment to achieve more satisfactory results.

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